

Geospatial Clean Cooking OnStove Modelling in Guatemala

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Executive Summary

Guatemala's Energy Policy Plan (2013-2027) aims to reduce firewood use and promote cleaner cooking technologies [2]. Despite their health and climate benefits, access to clean cooking remains limited. The study seeks to identify which technology offers the greatest net benefit for scaling wood-saving stoves in Guatemala. With a population of 17.3 million [3], 99.1% have electricity access, yet only 46.2% have access to clean cooking technologies [20]. Household air pollution is a significant issue, leading to thousands of deaths annually from respiratory and cardiovascular diseases [6].

The OnStove tool assesses and compares the net benefits of different cooking technologies using geospatial data. It considers benefits like health, environment, time savings, and costs such as capital, operation, and fuel.

The two scenarios studied were the social and private. The social scenario got the highest net benefits in electric stoves. The private scenario reveals a preference for LPG due to its lower costs compared to electricity. It suggests that reducing electricity tariffs could make electric cooking more attractive, especially for low-income households.

To foster clean cooking adoption, policies should combine economic incentives with support measures, focusing on making electric cooking more affordable.

1. Introduction

Clean cooking refers to the use of fuels that minimize adverse health effects associated with cooking. Globally, the importance of cooking technologies that minimize harmful emissions, improve thermal efficiency, and ensure safety and durability is widely recognized. These technologies are generally classified into three types: traditional, improved (ICS), and clean. The adoption of clean cooking is crucial for achieving SDG 7,

which advocates for affordable and clean energy, specifically under indicator 7.1.2, which focuses on the use of clean fuels and technologies.

This report presents a geospatial analysis of clean cooking technologies in Guatemala using the OnStove tool. The OnStove is a geospatial clean cooking tool used to determinate the net-benefit of cooking with different stoves across an area. Guatemala aims to reduce firewood use for cooking, promoting cleaner and more sustainable alternatives. Despite significant efforts, access to clean cooking technologies remains limited, posing health and environmental risks due to continued reliance on traditional biomass fuels. This study investigates which technology offers the highest net benefits when scaling wood-saving stoves across the country.

The study's results aim to inform policymakers about the necessary steps to enhance clean cooking adoption, reduce household air pollution, and improve public health outcomes in Guatemala.

2. Methodology

This study utilizes a geospatial clean cooking tool to determine the net benefit of adopting different types of stoves to enhance context. The traditional category includes biomass and charcoal stoves, the improved cookstove (ICS) category includes charcoal and biomass stoves, and the clean energy category includes electricity, biogas, and LPG stoves.

The methodology is structured around several key parameters, including morbidity and mortality reductions, emissions reductions, time savings, capital investments, operation and maintenance (O&M) costs, and fuel costs.

2.1. Data Collection:

Data on morbidity and mortality rates related to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, ischemic heart disease, stroke, lung cancer, and acute lower respiratory infections are collected. Emission data related to stove types, fuel production, and transportation, as well as time saved from increased cooking efficiency and reduced fuel collection, are gathered. Additionally, information on the capital costs of stoves, O&M costs, and fuel prices is collated.

2.2. Model Framework:

Integrate data into a model to estimate:

- Health Benefits: Reduction in disease cases and deaths.
- Emission Reductions: Lower emissions from stove-switching and fuel use.
- Time Savings: Time saved in cooking and fuel collection.
- Cost Analysis: Capital, O&M, and fuel costs for each stove.

2.3. Net-Benefit Calculation:

The net-benefit for each stove type is calculated for each settlement by combining the health benefits, emissions reductions, time savings, and cost factors. The stove with the highest net-benefit is selected for each settlement.

2.4. Scenarios:

2.4.1. Private Scenario: Focuses on individual household decisions, emphasizing direct benefits such as cost savings without considering broader environmental and societal impacts. It's crucial for understanding how households make decisions based on immediate, tangible benefits, which influences the adoption of clean cooking technologies.

2.4.2. Social Scenario: Considers the broader societal benefits, including government support and environmental impacts, when evaluating clean cooking technologies. It highlights the importance of collective benefits and long-term societal goals, which are essential for policymaking and achieving widespread adoption of sustainable technologies.

Balancing both scenarios helps in designing policies that address both individual needs and societal goals.

3. Results

Private Scenario

After modelling the private scenario, the analysis identified the optimal investment areas for each technology. Areas in red indicate the highest net benefit from electricity, while those in blue show the highest benefit from LPG. Dark green areas, indicate that biogas has the highest net-benefits, but is not available for the entire population and therefore the stove with the second highest net-benefit needs to be selected (LPG). This is also seen in the pink and orange areas, but instead with electricity. The summary statistics are presented annually, except for time saved, which is measured in hours per household per day.

Figure 1. Map of Maximum net- benefit for private scenario.

In the private scenario, LPG offers the highest net benefit to 54% of the population, while electricity benefits 46%. Population density plays a crucial role, explaining the discrepancy between the map in Figure 1 and the population split in Figure 2. The blue areas on the map represent urban regions with higher population density, contrasting with the more sparsely populated rural areas. Additionally, biogas is highlighted with 0%, indicating that it offers the highest net benefit to only a very small portion of the population.

Figure 2. Population split in the private scenario.

In the case of the private scenario the benefits from the LPG and the Electricity are higher than the costs which means that the total benefits as a country level are higher than the total costs in both cases.

Figure 3. Benefits vs costs for the private scenario.

From a net-benefit perspective, households with higher wealth should be provided with LPG due to its significant net benefits. Conversely, households with lower wealth should be supplied with electricity. Given the population density in the study area, it appears that most of the population would achieve the highest net benefit with LPG.

Figure 4. Wealth in the private scenario.

Social Scenario

The social scenario offers the highest net benefits compared to the private scenario. As illustrated in Figure 5, 99% of the population density would achieve the highest net benefit from electricity, while only 1% would benefit more from LPG. Additionally, Figure 6 shows that the total benefits from electricity are higher than those from LPG, with lower associated costs. For LPG, the benefits and costs are not as significant due to current environmental and spillover considerations. It is also important to note that LPG has a lower total cost, which may appear negligible due to the small population density (1%) benefiting from it.

Figure 5. Population split in the social scenario.

Figure 6. Benefits vs costs for the social scenario.

Unlike the private scenario, the wealth distribution graph in the social scenario shows that electricity (red) provides the highest net benefits for both lower and higher wealth households. However, only a small number of households would achieve the highest net benefit from LPG, as indicated in Figure 7, which pertains to the lower wealth segment.

Figure 7. Wealth in the social scenario.

4. Discussion

The geospatial analysis using the OnStove tool reveals that while over half of the population still relies on charcoal and biomass, these fuels do not offer the highest net benefits in any scenario. The analysis shows that electric stoves, especially under the

"Social" scenario where broader societal benefits are considered, provide the highest net benefit. This includes significant reductions in morbidity and mortality related to household air pollution, along with emissions reductions, time savings, and cost-effectiveness when considering subsidies and lower electricity tariffs. However, in the "Private" scenario, LPG stoves are favored due to their current affordability and accessibility, especially in the absence of supportive policies for electricity pricing.

Given the results, it is recommended that policies should focus on promoting electric cooking by leveraging subsidies, tax breaks, and financing options to make electric stoves more accessible. Lowering electricity tariffs is also critical to making electric cooking competitive with LPG, especially for low-income households. Additionally, exploring hybrid stove options that can switch between electric and other clean fuels might be beneficial in areas with unreliable electricity. The government could also consider increasing investments in grid infrastructure to ensure reliable and widespread electricity access, which is essential for the successful adoption of electric stoves.

The study faces several limitations. OnStove's reliance on comprehensive data means that any gaps or inaccuracies in input data could skew the results. Moreover, the tool does not account for fuel stacking, where households use multiple stove types, which is a common practice in many regions. This omission might lead to an overestimation of the benefits of a single stove type. Additionally, the study does not assume an improvement in electricity access rates. The tool also lacks the ability to identify the most affordable technology options for these areas, and the graphical outputs do not allow detailed analysis by specific regions or population groups, which limits its usefulness for localized policy decisions.

Future research should explore interventions that address the challenges identified in this study. For example, research could focus on the feasibility and impact of hybrid cooking solutions that integrate multiple fuel types, accommodating regions with unreliable electricity access. Additionally, studies on the effectiveness of various policy incentives, such as electricity subsidies or micro-financing for stove purchases, would provide valuable insights. Exploring the behavioural aspects of stove adoption, including the reasons behind fuel stacking and resistance to switching, could inform more tailored interventions. Moreover, understanding the implementation challenges, particularly in remote areas, would help in designing more effective and equitable clean cooking programs. Research could also focus on improving the granularity of geospatial tools like OnStove to allow for more detailed, localized analysis that can better inform policy at the community level.

5. Conclusion

To promote clean cooking in Guatemala, a strategic approach that combines policy support with economic incentives is essential. Electric stoves, identified as offering the highest net benefits in a societal context, should be encouraged through subsidies, tax breaks, and financing options to make them more accessible to the population. Lowering electricity tariffs is also crucial to make electric cooking more affordable, especially for low-income households, thereby reducing the preference for LPG, which is currently favored in cost-focused scenarios.

Given that over half of Guatemala's population relies on charcoal and biomass fuels that consistently rank lower in net benefit. There is a clear need for new policies to shift the population toward cleaner alternatives. The transition to clean cooking technologies must be made both feasible and attractive to the population, which will require coordinated efforts from the government, private sector, and international partners. By fostering the adoption of electric stoves and addressing economic barriers, Guatemala can significantly improve health outcomes, reduce environmental impacts, and ensure a more sustainable future for its people.

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